

Adaptive Learning: Enhancing Students' Academic Resilience in English Subjects

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Abstract. The study unfolded the experiences of English teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students. Moreover, it sought to explore and discover the on-hand experiences of teachers in adaptive learning, enhancing students' academic resilience in English subjects, and employed a phenomenological research design to determine the experiences and perceptions of the eight (8) participants. The generated themes on the aspects that risk students' academic resiliency in English subjects were the poor acquisition of basic skills, the fear of correction, and students' low self-esteem. Meanwhile, three themes emerged from the participants' responses regarding teachers' coping in promoting academic resilience in teaching English to students: providing direct instructions, broadening students' word connections, and providing meaningful feedback. Lastly, regarding the educational management insights drawn from the study, three themes emerged from the participants' responses: a need to enhance professional competence, the importance of giving compliments, and fostering a supportive learning environment. These themes implied that Teachers should promote an avenue for the learners to demonstrate learning, overcome challenges, and promote positive relationships. Moreover, the results provided comprehensive data for future research with similar scope.

KEY WORDS

1. resiliency 2. English subject 3. challenges 4. approach

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1. Introduction

In a perfect world, students would be energized and driven to achieve their potential and equipped to deal effectively with academic setbacks, study pressure, and stress in the school setting. Today's life is full of challenges and threats. If people do not equip themselves with the necessary abilities, they will face many problems. In the 21st century, a group of psychologists has realized that man must spend his mental energy on the positive aspects of his experience (Wang et al., 2021). When people hear the word resilience, the thoughts that come to mind are bouncing back and beating the odds. Masten (1994) defined resilience as Positive adaptation to adversity despite serious threats to adaptation or development. When an individual is able to attain his or her normal development even in conditions that are adversely affecting him or her, he/she can be regarded as more resilient. A resilient individual beat the odds, and he also possessed the ability to change the odds. Resilience Research Centre (2016) defined resilience as being sensitive to ecological and cultural aspects to a greater extent. They define

it as: In the context of exposure to significant adversity, resilience is both the capacity of individuals to navigate their way to the psychological, social, cultural, and physical resources that sustain their well-being and their capacity individually and collectively to negotiate for these resources to be provided in culturally meaningful ways. In America, Alva (2000) conducted a study to establish a relationship between support from friends and educational support from teachers with the academic resilience of students. His sample contained Mexican American students. His findings suggested that students who received better support from teachers and friends outperformed their counterparts. Further, he declared that highly resilient students behaved better in group interpersonal relationships. He also concluded that these students enjoyed attending school, and their participation in school activities was better than their counterparts. In Urbana, Benard (2000) found that a child's participation in home activities plays a fundamental role in a child's resilience. He stated that meaningful participation is a fundamental human need. Benard established a relationship between participation in home activities and academic goals. He emphasized that a school can provide numerous curriculum and extracurricular activities in the same direction. He concluded that in this way, a student can learn critical thinking and dialogue. Students can benefit from participatory studies. Hanson Austin (2003) conducted a longitudinal study exploring the relationship between academic resilience and concurrent test scores in California. Schools with students who are resilient also reported high scores on tests. They concluded that there is a positive correlation between every measure of resilience and test scores. Further, they concluded that development in resilience is important and very useful in improving successive test scores. In the Philippines, a study conducted by Leysa (2016) revealed that students tend to be more resilient when they worry more about school and their fear of failure. Moreover, the extent of perceived control they have over their learning experiences does not signify the level of their resilience when it comes to schoolwork. Consistent with the literature, academic resilience predicts the desirable educational outcomes of enjoyment in school, class participation, and general self-esteem. Academic resilience among students has likewise been extensively researched and was defined as an increased likelihood of (academic) success despite environmental adversities. Resilient students maintain high motivational achievement and performance even when faced with stressful events and conditions that place them at risk of poor performance. Developments in resilience research indicate that individual resilience is not fixed; it is influenced and can be developed through innovative pedagogies and supportive social and living environments, particularly in schools (Alva, 2000). In the local setting, the rising incidence of mental health problems among high school students is an alarming trend. To date, however, researchers and practitioners have focused on the energy and drive of students and not so much on their ability to deal with pressure and setbacks. That is, there has been a focus on motivating students but not so much on enhancing their academic resilience. This study provided knowledge and information that promotes academic resilience in students. It was to see how English language teachers promote academic resilience to help students battle academic problems and difficulties to be successful and remove inferiority in themselves with regard to academic capabilities. This study aimed to explore the experiences of English language teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students. Factors that promoted or hindered academic resilience across the academic competence domain were investigated.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The study aimed to explore the experiences of English

language teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students. In the desire to provide students with a safe learning environment, attention needs to be given to both the external environment – the sources of challenges and support; and the internal environment – knowing what dimensions of resilience the students are lacking and focusing interventions on those areas. The researcher needed to study if the school is providing a safe learning

environment for students – not just to survive but to thrive.

1.2. Research Questions—This study sought to explore and discover the on-hand experiences of teachers on adaptive learning: enhancing students' academic resilience in English subjects and delivering students' academic performance. This study would specifically be aimed to answer the following questions:

- (1) What aspects risk students' academic resiliency in English subjects?
- (2) How do teachers cope with promoting academic resilience in teaching English to students?
- (3) What educational insights are drawn from the study?

This study may be significant to the following: DepEd Officials. The study's findings helped policymakers develop a model that can assist educators in developing students' academic resilience and that can also be easily explained to students. School Administrators. The study's findings gave them ideas on what technical assistance to give to teachers to promote students' academic resilience in English language subjects. Further, they provided a basis for strategic planning and detailed practice involving the whole school community to help vulnerable young people do better than their circumstances might have predicted. Teachers. This study's findings were helpful in that it exposed teachers to many conceptual perspectives, which, by implication, opens up new pathways for intervention. Moreover, having insight into students' risk factors enables teachers to choose appropriate teaching strategies and guide poor and failing students in a better way. Moreover, they adjust their teaching techniques to incorporate students' differences. In this way, they were able to motivate students to learn intrinsically. Future Researchers. The findings generated provided comprehensive data for future research with similar or relevant scope.

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were defined for use in this study: Aca-

ademic Resilience- It refers to students achieving good educational outcomes despite adversity. Adaptive Learning refers to the ability to change to suit changing conditions.

1.4. Review of Significant Literature—This section reviews key studies related to academic resilience and self-efficacy.

1.4.1. Academic Resilience—Resilience is the ability to overcome adversity and succeed academically. Duckworth's "grit" and Dweck's "growth mindset" are significant constructs in this area, showing that persistence and a belief in personal development contribute to academic success (Duckworth, 2009; Dweck, 2010). Academic buoyancy, distinct from resilience, helps students manage everyday academic setbacks (Martin Marsh, 2008). Resilient students tend to show high self-efficacy, persistence, and planning, and they view challenges as opportunities (Waxman et al., 2003).

1.4.2. Resilience and Self-efficacy—Academic resilience is closely related to self-efficacy, which refers to belief in one's ability to succeed. Bandura (1995) emphasized self-efficacy as a key factor in academic performance, especially in adversity. High self-efficacy increases motivation and perseverance, helping students reject negative thoughts and overcome challenges (Ozer Bandura, 1990).

1.4.3. Motivation and Resilience—Motivation plays a crucial role in resilience. Kim Kim (2016) found that persistence in EFL learners is linked to higher motivation and language proficiency. Additionally, resilience helps students cope with language learning demotivation. Covington Omelich (1991) highlighted different student typologies: success-oriented, failure-avoidant, and failure-accepting, where success-oriented students exhibit greater resilience.

1.4.4. Risk Factors for Academic Resilience—Several factors risk students' resilience, including poor acquisition of basic skills (Boyd, 2006), fear of correction (Yalçın İnceçay, 2019), and adverse childhood experiences (Felitti et al., 1998). A negative learning environment and performance pressure can also hinder academic performance (Rachh, 2022).

1.4.5. Coping Strategies for Academic Resilience—Teachers can foster resilience through direct instruction, providing meaningful feedback, and creating a supportive learning environment (Graham, 2012; Brown, 2001). Positive relationships with peers and adults, especially teachers, also contribute to students' academic resilience (Crosnoe Elder, 2004). Building self-belief and valuing school further strengthen students' resilience and motivation to succeed (Bandura, 1997; McInerney, 2000).

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on Heider's Attribution Theory and Control (1958). According to attribution theory, the causes individuals attribute to events can determine how they behave on future occasions. In the classroom, a student's attributions influence his or her optimism, performance, and affect. The perceived cause of an outcome is hypothesized to vary primarily along three dimensions: locus, stability, and controllability. The issue of control is the focus of this paper because it primarily determines students' responses to setbacks, pressure, or fear of failure and, by implication, is relevant to a model of motivation and academic resilience. Control refers to

how students feel they can avoid failure and achieve success. Students who feel they have little or no control over outcomes are increasingly uncertain whether they can avoid failure or bring about success. In response to this, they may engage in counterproductive behavior (self-sabotage) or may give up altogether (e.g., become learned helplessness). On the other hand, high control is linked to students' persistence, attention, effort, participation, mastery motivation, and achievement (Connell, 1993). This evidence suggested that students low in perceived control are not inclined to engage in behavior consistent with adaptive motivation. Moreover, it seems that students who are low in control may lack resilience to academic setbacks because such setbacks may have the effect of confirming their doubts about themselves. In response to this uncertainty and doubt, they have been found to engage in counterproductive academic behavior (Martin et al., 2001). From attribution and control theory perspectives (in addition to predictions by need achievement and self-worth motivation perspectives), control is a construct important to include in a motivation and academic resilience model. Another theory that supported this study was the Self-Efficacy Theory of Bandura (1977). Students who are high in self-efficacy tend to generate and test alternative courses of action when they do not meet with initial success, function better in the classroom through elevated levels of effort and persistence, and deal more effectively with problem situations by influencing cognitive and emotional processes related to those situations. Students low in self-efficacy tend to dwell on their deficiencies and view situations as more complex than they are (Bandura, 1997). It can be said with some confidence that self-belief is critical to a student's motivation and resilience. The student with a strong sense of self-belief is energized to perform (i.e., is motivated) and, in the face of challenge, believes in his or her ability to surmount it (i.e., academically re-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the study

silient). The evidence supports this assertion: Self-efficacy and self-belief have been linked to such outcomes as self-regulation, effort, persistence, and achievement. Self-belief is, therefore, a construct directly relevant to the motivation and academic resilience model being developed here. Further, the Expectancy X Value Theory of Atkinson (1960) was another way of conceptualizing self-belief in terms of expectancy: students who believe they can master their schoolwork also have positive expectations for success. Along the lines of self-belief, students' expectations for academic outcomes are connected to their motivation and achievement. What further contributes to students' motivation is their valuing of a task. Moreover, the interaction of their expectations and their valuing of a given task predict their motivation for it such that those with high expectations and who also value the

task are most motivated to do it. This interaction is conceptualized in the expectancy x value theory. Another important component of motivation and academic resilience is the value of schooling and the tasks within it. When students see the utility and importance of what they are taught, they tend to be more engaged in these subjects and achieve at a higher level. The value of schooling can also help students to endure tough times in the way that it predicts intentions and willingness to continue with studies in the future. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are (1) aspects that risk students' academic resiliency in English subjects, (2) ways for teachers to cope with promoting academic resilience in teaching English to students, and (3) educational insights drawn from the study.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study, including selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher utilized artificial intelligence (AI) methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation, explicitly leveraging AI to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is communicated openly to adhere to ethical norms in research, underscoring a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledging AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It established the background for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. This study explored the realities of English teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participants' answers in the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This is the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), stated that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggested that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' This study intended to gather information from the

experiences of English teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students. The researcher followed the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). It was assured that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology. This was the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) stated that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggested that the researcher openly discussed values that shaped the narrative and included his or her interpretation in conjunction with the participants' interpretation. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher wrote in a literary, informal style using the personal voice, using qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to understand how stakeholders' partnerships in school-initiated programs were built and maintained between schools and the surrounding community.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). This study explored the lived experiences and perspectives of English teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students, particularly the English teachers from Leon Garcia Sr., National High School, Division of Davao City. The researcher was driven to know the deeper meaning of their experi-

ences, which became the basis for qualitative research. It was considered helpful in looking for meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers so that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research is that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By using phenomenology, which concerns the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as the basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design since it focused on the lived experiences of English teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students. Creswell (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focusing on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand

knowledge of an event, situation or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempted to extract the purest, untainted data, and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing was used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occurred when researchers asked one or more participants general, open-ended questions and recorded their answers. Often audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were useful to follow-up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In this qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees will say (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews were particularly useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected

data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textual description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The researcher needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations were to be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were a powerful tool for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the realities of English language teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students, the researcher intended to employ phenomenological methods of qualitative research.

2.4. Research Participants—The participants of this study were the eight (8) English

language teachers of Carmen District, Division of Davao Del Norte. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the present position for at least five years—regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; (2) must be teaching English subject; and (3) and must have at least very satisfactory rating in their IPCRF. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needed to adhere to the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. Research is essential to the society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was specifically conducted among English language teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the researcher's interest is the challenges the English language teachers face in promoting academic resilience among high school students. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study.

Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as a researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they have queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered conveniently. The dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each in-

formant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there were no conflicts of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased way, was avoided.

Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results.

Transparency. The study's results were accessed by the participants and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and was placed on CD or other storage devices, which the researcher could request to provide. In addition, by learning from the study's results, English language teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each of the participants was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their individual transcript after the interview is carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information which they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and changing names and or non-

significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possessed the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher was qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to complete the study successfully in the specified time and was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher expressed great pleasure in the interviewees' wholehearted participation in the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included or that conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher took up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducted interviews with the participants and guided them in the process. The researcher interpreted ideas and responded based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assessed himself and sought help from the research adviser and other professionals. These helped him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher were secured adequately as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research began. Analyst of data. The researcher saw the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensured that

the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. The researcher organized and presented the data, as well as the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. The findings of the study were presented, too, by the research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gave future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. Research Instrument—In gathering data, the researcher utilized an in-depth interview questionnaire. The researcher developed the interview questionnaire, which was answered by the participants orally. These researcher-made interview questionnaires were developed upon consultation and validation by the experts and underwent several processes to accommodate their suggestions. The components to be validated include the language and the conceptual levels of questions if suited to the participant's level of understanding, the suitability of the items to the research design in which there should be no leading questions, and the alignment of the interview questions to the objective of the study.

2.8. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the response of the SDS before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools.

Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data were then categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.9. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualita-

tive analysis. It involves generating pithy labels for essential features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature. The researcher explored the experiences of English language teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substituted data trustworthiness, which consists of components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility involved establishing that the research findings were credible or believable from the participant's perspective. Observing the attributes of prolonged engagement was where credibility contributed to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the credibility issue, the researcher interviewed as many research participants as possible or up

to the point of saturation. Meanwhile, transferability was the degree to which the findings were generalized or transferred to other contexts. In this, the researcher did a thorough job of describing the research context and relevant assumptions. On the other hand, dependability was the consistency and repeatability of the research. The researcher ensured that the study's findings were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability was the degree to which other researchers could confirm or corroborate findings. The researcher documented the procedures and rechecked the data during the entire research process. The researcher also ensured that the findings were free from bias.

2.11. Analytical Framework—The framework analysis of this research was flexible, allowing the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. The gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted in the analysis stage under key issues and themes. Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher became familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation or field notes) and gained an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher became immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher became aware of critical ideas and recurrent themes and noted them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may not be able to review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set was utilized. The selection depends on several aspects of the data collection process—for example, the mix of methods used (e.g., interviews, documents, observations). The second stage, identifying a thematic framework, occurs after familiarization, when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, at this stage, the researcher allowed the data to dictate the themes and issues. The researcher used the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this end. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying portions or sections of the data that correspond to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used to index references and annotated in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping

and interpretation, involved the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis provided a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in interpreting the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: "defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies" (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflected the participant. Therefore, the researcher's strategy or recommendations echoed the participants' true attitudes, beliefs, and values. Figure 2 shows the steps in the study's analytical framework, which involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the study's results with reference to its aim. It also discusses the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The results present the description and background of the participants who were assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

*3.1. Aspects that Risk Students' Academic Resiliency in English Subject—*Language is a means of communication that transmits information, ideas, or feelings from one person to another. Because of its importance, people need to learn it. English is one of the languages used in all parts of the world. It is used widely; almost all countries use it either as the first, second, or foreign language. As an international language, English has become an important subject to be mastered by Filipino students, either for communicative or academic purposes. Teaching English in high school has its challenges. The participants experienced these aspects that potentially risked students' resiliency in the subject. The participants' responses were narrowed down into one to generate the themes and sub-themes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants' accounts and reflections.

*3.1.1. Poor acquisition of basic skills—*The participants shared that the students find English a challenging subject to learn. The language features grammatical rules that are often broken, an alphabet that can confuse people who are used to a character-based system, and spelling and pronunciation irregularities that perplex even native speakers. The participants further stated that this difficulty in understanding may primarily be caused by insufficient acquisition of basic English concepts in their key stage 1 and 2 learning phases. This corroborated Boyd's (2006) idea that many concepts and topics of the higher secondary school curriculum can be difficult to understand and prepare for without expert supervision. Missing classes when such topics are taught may be unfortunate for the child, thus affecting the over-

all academic score. According to Megawati (2016), three elements are essential in learning the English language, especially in supporting four English skills: pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar. However, students have difficulty learning these skills.

*3.1.2. The Fear of Correction—*The findings imply that anxious students felt a deep self-consciousness when asked to speak English in the presence of other people. According to the participants, the students worried much about the errors they might be committing when using the language, and they did not like being laughed at or making a fool of themselves in public, especially in front of someone they knew. The common response of the participants implied that in English classes students tried to avoid activities like recitation, speech delivery, and the like since speaking needed to be spontaneous, and learners find it embarrassing on their part when the entire class hears every single mistake they committed. The fear of correction is attributed to the fact that students do not want to be criticized and corrected in front of the whole class. Even in writing activities, students were embarrassed and afraid to see their outputs evaluated as having many errors and appearing with too many red marks. Filipino learners usually associate red marks with negative feelings because these are evidence of error corrections and, thus, poor performance. Filipino learners' anxious thoughts about using the language and of corrections keep them focused on their learning difficulties, which, in turn, might affect their learning process. The distraction caused by negative thoughts keeps them from focusing on the task at hand, causing them to suffer from an inability to process, continue, or complete and

even express a train of thought. This finding supported the study of Yalçın İnceçay (2019) which showed that anxious foreign language Turkish students identify speaking in the target language as the most frightening language skill and that they feel stressed and even start to freeze when they have to act out a role-play or deliver a speech. Similarly, in a study by Liu Jackson (2020), Chinese learners of English as a foreign language were unwilling to communicate. They revealed that most of their participants were willing to participate in interpersonal conversations. However, they did not like the risk of using or speaking in English in class. Speaking in a foreign language is often cited by students as their most anxiety-producing experience, and also, difficulty in speaking in class is probably the most frequently cited concern of anxious foreign language students. Furthermore, the participants added that when Filipino learners are asked to speak in front of the class, they feel more vulnerable because of the fear that their foreign language weaknesses will be exposed to their teacher and classmates, causing them to lose self-esteem. This further supported the concept that second language classroom anxiety and language-skill-specific anxieties are two relatively independent constructs, each with unique characteristics. Still, they share commonalities such as a negative effect on certain aspects of communication, avoidance of certain kinds of social exchanges, and fear of being evaluated (Jugo, 2020).

3.1.3. Students' low self-esteem—Many factors may influence the students' learning in English subjects, such as their grammar, vocabulary, ideas, and personality, as well as their self-esteem. It has been known that learning English is not easy. It is hard enough to develop an idea into a paragraph and follow the rules of the text. These factors can cause the students to think they cannot do it. They do not believe in their ability. The participants expressed that this personality is the main problem for the stu-

dents when they start learning English. In other words, one factor that might influence students to write is their self-esteem; the participants point out that self-esteem guides their behavior, influences attitudes, and drives their motivation to learn. The statements above pointed out that the student's anxiety and sense of fatalism about learning the subject may impede their ability to perform effectively. English teachers admitted that they apply some techniques along with the guided approach so that the students can master them more easily. Unfortunately, students' attitudes and beliefs are growing factors. The participants believe that their peers are also contributing factors to their self-esteem. For the participants, English language teachers were an important part of establishing and maintaining healthy environments for students to learn and grow. They must help students who are not confident in themselves or who are afraid to make a mistake to build their feelings of confidence. They also stated that they can play an important role in referring students experiencing low self-esteem to professionals who can be of assistance. This corroborated with the findings of Brown (2000) who states no successful cognitive and affective activity can be carried out without some degree of self-esteem, self-confidence, knowledge of oneself and belief in one's own capabilities for that activity. Self-esteem affects students English learning achievement by making the students be more confident and have more motivation in learning process. According to Lederman (2010), students sometimes feel overwhelmed by instructor feedback and don't know where to begin to improve their performance, which is one cause of low self-esteem. He suggested that it is most effective if a teacher makes it clear to students that each assignment's feedback is meant to help them but that on formal assignments, they will be assessed along multiple dimensions, which the teacher needs to spell out clearly. In Figure 3 below, three themes emerged from the par-

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Aspects that Risk Students’ Academic Resiliency in English Subject

participants’ responses: poor acquisition of basic skills, the fear of correction, and students’ low self-esteem. These themes implied that students must develop not only the component skills and knowledge necessary to perform complex tasks but also their emotional aspects, and then they must practice integrating these aspects to de-

velop greater fluency in learning the English subject. Students must learn when and how to apply the skills and knowledge they learn. As teachers, it is essential to develop a conscious awareness of these elements of mastery to help students learn more effectively.

3.2. *Teachers’ Coping in Promoting Academic Resilience in Learning English to Students*—English subject is an essential component of a balanced curriculum, providing an additional supported step towards independent learning. As an activity, it should be carefully targeted towards groups of students according to their current targets or specific needs. Teachers should consider carefully the purpose of the guided session and select the students accordingly. The aim is to provide support that will help students improve their resiliency in learning the subject and work with increasing independence.

3.2.1. *Providing direct instructions*—The participants stated that there is a need to introduce students to different strategies for teaching English subjects so they understand there is more than one way to approach learning. They asserted that students do not need to memorize all the possible contexts of English. Instead, they should understand its purpose and know how to select an appropriate strategy that suits them best. Furthermore, the participants also

stressed that teachers should provide some form of learning stimulus in providing direct instruction. This stimulus, for them, is like a prompt that introduces and focuses on learning a topic. This is to encourage the student’s interest in a topic and encourage them to learn its context thoughtfully and creatively. They claimed that an effective prompt introduces and directs the learning of the subject; it also provides clear instructions about their task. The participants also like to modify their instruction based on their students’ skill levels. For example, when working with struggling students who are new to learning English, like writing, they begin by presenting a basic version of a strategy, like setting one goal for essay length. When students become more comfortable with it, they challenge them to extend the strategy further by setting additional or more difficult goals. Graham (2012) noted that since English is a complex subject, students can become more effective learners and see themselves as resilient when they learn to use strategies for different stages of the learning process. Direct teaching strategies, such

as enhancing word choice, sentence combining, adding detail, and revising based on feedback, help students build a toolbox of strategies to improve their English learning. Using a direct instruction method can help deepen understanding of these individual strategies by teaching them through developing students' Background Knowledge, discussing the strategy, modeling it, memorizing it, supporting it, and providing independent practice. Hence, it is important that as students learn new strategies, they have scaffolded support to master and independently apply them. Teachers can create activities with explicit strategies and multiple stages to develop skills. Direct instruction is the cornerstone of effective instruction. It facilitates the process of learning. Teachers can plan projects, tasks, and classes so that students can work together to achieve a common goal. It also enables teachers to give clear directions, illustrations, explanations, and descriptions. This kind of instruction allows students to easily define learning objectives, activities, and goals and review and adapt to changing circumstances. Teachers can start a lesson by introducing the main idea to the class and then check whether the students are ready to practice the skills and concepts you presented. They can accomplish this by asking students questions to see whether they understand or by having them work in small groups to write down some crucial ideas on a large piece of paper on the wall or the whiteboard/blackboard in the classroom. After double-checking their students' comprehension, they can propose a short- or long-term project in which students can build on, apply, and review what they have learned in class, individually or as a team (Augustine, 2022).

3.2.2. Broadening students' word connections—The participants voiced that it is essential to develop students' word acquisition in order for them to successfully put in print the thoughts and ideas they wanted to share. They stated that they have vocabulary drills, reading

comprehension activities, spelling drills, and many more every class session since they believe these activities can broaden the students' world of words, improving their English learning skills. The participants also believed that students should repetitively use the words they learned in order for them to store it in their long-term memory. One way to use it is to associate words with their experiences or memories so that they can recall them as they have influenced their life. This is to improve students' associative memory, where they can practice retrieval of associations, which helps strengthen synaptic connections in the brain and enhances their ability to recall it more quickly. This corroborated the idea of Cuncic (2021), who asserted that the value of developing associative memory capabilities has far-reaching implications for their daily life. Establishing associations helps people remember information more easily, such as names and places, phone numbers, birthdays, and anniversaries. This may help them recall other related information about themselves. It also helps people to remember things in an efficient manner by recalling information that is useful for specific tasks. If students can spell, recognize, and use a word in the proper format, written and verbally, they have mastered that word. According to Joshi Roth (2009), the true goal of the English learning system reaches beyond spelling and pronunciation in communication, and the final test is whether or not meaning can be conveyed and understood in written or oral. English can be tricky because many words sound the same when pronounced but are spelled differently and have a completely different meaning. For example, the words rain, rein and reign all have very different meanings, but all sound the same and may be confusing for a user of English vocabulary. Because the English language is complex to master, the best way to achieve true understanding is to establish a connection between reading comprehension, vocabulary, and spelling. The path to reading

and writing fluently in English is mastering the connections between letter combinations and the sounds they represent.

3.2.3. Providing Meaningful Feedback— The participants stressed that feedback is a key element of the incremental process of students learning performance and resiliency. Providing frequent and ongoing feedback is a significant means of improving student achievement and resiliency in learning. They believe that effective feedback assists the students in reflecting on their learning and their learning strategies so they can make adjustments to make better progress. Further, they shared that when students are trying to learn new skills, they must get information that tells them whether or not they are doing the right thing. Both the mastery of content and, more importantly, how to think require trial-and-error learning. However, for them, there is also a downside to feedback as not all can be effective, especially if presented solely negatively or correctly. Moreover, timely feedback is necessary for the participant so that students would still have fresh associations and reflections on the feedback given. This finding was congruent with the notion of Brown (2001), who asserted that giving feedback in the process of learning English is important to improve students' learning quality. Giving feedback to students is essential. It is given as a source of information about the student's strengths and weaknesses in their learning to make improvements. Feedback is information that is given to the learner with the objective of improving the

3.3. Educational Insights are Drawn from the Study— The participants shared their educational management insights, and it was narrowed down into one to generate the themes. These themes were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants' accounts and reflections.

performance. Giving feedback means telling learners about the progress they are making as well as guiding them to areas for improvement. Through feedback given, learners are expected to be able to focus and concentrate more on what is being learned. Furthermore, feedback given by a teacher makes learners more aware of their strengths and weaknesses in a learning course, so they are expected to use their strengths to overcome their weaknesses by understanding the feedback given. In addition, Ferris (2000) claimed that corrective feedback on students' learning is effective in improving their skills. Corrections cannot be dismissed in general, as they depend on the quality of the correction; if the correction is clear and consistent, it will work. The combination of written and conference feedback can significantly improve students' writing accuracy levels by using the past simple tense and the definite article in a new piece of writing. In Figure 4 below, three themes emerged from the participants: providing direct instructions, broadening students' word connections, and providing meaningful feedback. These themes implied that teachers should provide students with opportunities to develop their several English learning skills, as it is the fundamental skill needed in writing a well-versed composition. An English teacher may identify learners' weaknesses and strengths and provide valuable input to enhance their learning skills. Measuring and knowing students' performance in classes is essential in teaching English.

3.3.1. A need to enhance professional competence— The participants stressed the importance of educating the teachers' minds. It helps the teachers to keep their professional knowledge and skills updated. The new generations have a different approach to learning than the previous generations. Professional development helps teachers learn new techniques for teach-

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on Teachers’ Coping in Promoting Academic Resilience in Learning English to Students

ing students of this generation, particularly in improving their English learning performance. For them, trainings, seminars, and LAC sessions encourage the exchange of knowledge and best teaching practices. Seasoned teachers can act as mentors to new ones, and the new teachers can provide the seasoned teachers with up-to-date knowledge of the latest teaching styles and modes. Furthermore, through professional development, teachers can acquire skills on how to integrate technology effectively into English instruction. Technology is the latest trend nowadays; the participants believe that technology interests students; hence, teachers should maximize its potential use in improving their performance in English subjects. Today’s teaching careers look nothing like they did 20 or even just 10 years ago. Like technology, the field of education evolves so fast that techniques, skills, and technologies become obsolete within five to 10 years. That is why being a lifelong learner plays an important role in the educational process. It helps educators incorporate new tools and strategies into the learning process to boost their students’ learning development. Lifelong learning is an essential challenge for inventing the future of societies; it is a necessity rather than a luxury to be considered. It is a mindset and a habit for people to acquire (Fischer, 2018). Educators who are lifelong learners are more successful. They can conquer challenges.

People with a lifelong learning mindset treat mistakes and challenges as part of the learning process. They do not see mistakes as failures. Mistakes give them new information they can use as they continue to find ways to solve a problem or challenge. Educators never know what types of questions students will ask. Lifelong learners make learning a regular habit to adapt to changes and student actions. By embracing a student-like mindset and learning to turn self-education into a daily habit, teachers can hone their current skills and develop new ones while enriching their minds. Then, when the time to adapt arrives, the transitions are less bumpy (Jun, 2018).

3.3.2. *The importance of giving compliments*—Teachers are often puzzled about what to do when students do not try to learn or become discouraged by setbacks or material they perceive to be too difficult. One cause of this behavior is many students’ mindsets about their intelligence. This demonstrates that students having the mindset that they are either smart or not smart has serious negative consequences for learning. The participants believed that one powerful way they can intervene as teachers is by being careful about how they praise students. Offering praise for students’ work and efforts can alter this mindset so that students can begin to view their intelligence as something that can be developed. This mindset of develop-

ing intelligence will increase students' ability to "bounce back" in the face of academic setbacks and other difficulties. Praise was one of the simplest and most powerful tools to engage and motivate students. When used effectively, praise can turn around behavior challenges and improve students' attitudes about learning. Students who learn and think differently often receive negative feedback because of their struggles. That makes meaningful and appropriate praise even more important. The participants also viewed that although praise is important, it must not be overused and used effectively. The participants' responses corroborated Fagell (2020)'s statement that compliments can be positive reinforcement for students' efforts and achievements in learning English. When students receive compliments, it boosts their confidence and motivates them to continue learning and improving their language skills. Compliments can also create a sense of belonging and validation for students. Teachers complimenting students on their language skills shows that their efforts and progress are recognized and valued. This can help students feel more connected to their classmates and teachers, increasing their learning motivation. Compliments can encourage students to take risks and challenge themselves in language learning. When students receive compliments for their language skills, it shows that their efforts are paying off and they can succeed. This can give students the confidence to try new things and take on new challenges in their language learning. Furthermore, Hattie and Timperley (2011), in their Power of Positive Feedback article, discussed the importance of providing feedback to students that is both specific and positive. The authors argue that positive feedback can significantly impact student motivation and learning outcomes. Ulanoff, Christensen, Kehle (2011) concluded that positive reinforcement can significantly impact student motivation but needs to be genuine, specific, and linked to perfor-

mance.

3.3.3. *Foster a supportive learning environment*—The participant reiterated the importance of fostering a learning environment in which students feel safe, relaxed, and willing to take risks, especially for learners who may have had negative experiences and poor learning resilience in traditional classroom environments. Students often describe supportive learning environments as expanding their sense of family and enhancing their self-esteem, which, when combined with increased literacy skills, help students take more chances in pursuing their goals. The participants firmly believed that students' determination and belief that they can achieve their goals are important factors in their persistence in ongoing learning. Teachers need to provide students with a safe and supportive classroom environment that facilitates the active participation and engagement of all students. This corroborated the idea that when educators foster safe, loving, and close relationships with students, kids are more open to learning. Relationships are the key to motivating them. When students become open to learning, a culture of accountability and self-regulation can occur. Hall Souers (2002) refer to the safe and welcoming learning environment as "the nest." The idea of prioritizing safety and building a safe classroom nest is not new. Abraham Maslow introduced his hierarchy of needs, which explained that safety is the essential external factor influencing our happiness, success, and very survival beyond the basic physiological needs we have as human beings. Becton (2005) also agrees with this idea; she asserted that positive, productive learning environments are critical to students' academic, emotional, and social success. Unfortunately, positive learning environments do not just happen independently—they must be created. Many components go into making a positive learning environment for students. For starters, positive learning environments should offer a climate of safety, where risk-taking is encour-

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on the Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Study

aged, open, authentic conversation, trust, and respect are fostered, and positive interaction is the norm. In Figure 5 below, three themes emerged from the participants’ responses: the need to enhance professional competence, giving compliments, and fostering a supportive learning

environment. These themes implied that teachers should improve their students’ and their own competence. Teachers should promote an avenue for the learners to demonstrate learning, overcome challenges, and promote positive relationships.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study, followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in the field of teachers’ experiences are also discussed here.

4.1. *Findings*—This study sought to explore and discover the on-hand experiences of teachers on adaptive learning: enhancing students’ academic resilience in English subjects and delivering students’ academic performance. The participants of this study were the eight (8) English language teachers of Carmen District, Division of Davao Del Norte. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the present position for at least five years- regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; (2) must be teaching English subject; and (3) and must have at least very satisfactory rating in their IPCRF. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study.

moting academic resilience among high school students. Three themes were drawn from the participant’s responses on the aspects that risk students’ academic resiliency in English subjects: poor acquisition of basic skills, the fear of correction, and students’ low self-esteem. These themes implied that students must develop not only the component skills and knowledge necessary to perform complex tasks but also their emotional aspect, and then they must practice integrating these aspects to develop greater fluency in learning English. Students must learn when and how to apply the skills and knowledge they learn. As teachers, it was essential to develop a conscious awareness of these elements of mastery to help students learn more effectively. Moreover, regarding teachers’ coping in promoting academic resilience in teaching English to students, three themes

4.2. *Implications*—The study aimed to explore the experiences of English teachers in pro-

emerged from the participants' responses: providing direct instructions, broadening students' word connections, and providing meaningful feedback. These themes implied that teachers should provide students with opportunities to develop their several skills in English learning, as it was the fundamental skill needed in writing a well-versed composition. An English teacher may identify learners' weaknesses and strengths and provide valuable input to enhance their learning skills. Measuring and knowing students' performance in classes was a must in teaching English. Lastly, regarding the educational management insights drawn from the study, three themes emerged from the participants' responses: the need to enhance professional competence, the importance of giving compliments and fostering a supportive learning environment. These themes implied that teachers should improve not just their students' competence but also their own. Teachers should promote an avenue for the learners to demonstrate learning, overcome challenges, and promote positive relationships.

4.3. *Future Directions*—The data obtained had directions for various educational stakeholders, including policymakers, administrators, and teachers. The future directions of this

study were as follows: The study's goal was to explore the experiences of English teachers in promoting academic resilience among high school students. Policymakers may synergize better with school leaders and teacher trainers so that policies about promoting academic resilience among high school students will be implemented. School administrators may evaluate the strategies for promoting resiliency in teaching English subjects. They may also facilitate teachers' work, especially by providing technical support. Teachers may expand their strategies to promote resiliency in learning English with research-based outcomes. Teachers may develop students' attitudes, motivation, and enjoyment of learning English to produce quality learning outcomes. Teaching writing and developing not just students' writing skills but also their attitudes, motivation, and enjoyment of producing writing that is relevant to today's standards. Future researchers may consider other perspectives, such as educators in other subject areas, and conduct more interviews with students and teachers in other grade levels. This would yield advantageous findings and implications tailored to the organization and hierarchical context of the education sector.

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